

FACTORS OF FORMING STUDENTS' SCIENTIFIC FORECASTING SKILLS IN TEACHING PHILOSOPHY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17808770>

Abstract. *The problem of the philosophical and pedagogical justification of the development of the educational sphere and its social effectiveness at the present stage on the basis of educational paradigms is relevant. The task of forecasting in the provision and control of education by future teachers serves the organization of the educational process and the anticipation of its future, as well as obtaining information based on strategic analysis. This makes it possible to predict whether specific knowledge, qualifications, and skills intended for a certain part of the educational material are sufficiently formed at each stage of instruction. The article also examines the factors of forming students' forecasting skills based on the philosophy of teaching.*

Keywords: *effectiveness, skill, forecasting, ability, knowledge, philosophy, approach, competence, goal.*

Introduction

In philosophy, scientific forecasting is an integral part of an effective pedagogical process, ensuring the systematization of knowledge, the development of plans, and the creation of favorable conditions for learning. This process encompasses a wide range of methods and approaches aimed at advancing and adapting educational requirements, thereby contributing to high quality and sustainability in the educational process. Today, students must not only possess acquired professional knowledge and practical skills, but also develop competencies that enable them to think critically, make independent decisions, act quickly in situations of uncertainty, demonstrate effective results, and find non-standard solutions to professional tasks. The philosopher and scholar Professor N. Mukhamadiev suggests teaching philosophical disciplines in accordance with professional characteristics in the following sequence: “philosophy of nature, philosophy of technology and information technologies, philosophy of medicine, philosophy of economic competition, philosophy of law, philosophy of military martial arts, philosophy of information security and technologies, philosophy of culture and art, philosophy of education and upbringing, philosophy of history, philosophy of politics” [3].

Among the Central Asian philosophers and thinkers who worked in India, Iran, and Afghanistan, an important place belongs to Mirzo Abdulqadir Bedil. He was born in 1644 in the city of Azimabad in India and devoted his life to science and literature in India. His philosophical works such as “*Chor Unsur*” (“Four Elements”), “*Nuqot*”, “*Irfan*”, as well as a number of works related to literary studies have been preserved. In the philosophy of Berdil, the study of human cognitive capacities holds a special place. According to him, the first stage of cognition—its essence and possibilities is closely connected with a person's sensory qualities. Human sensory qualities are individual in nature. Therefore, each person possesses limited sensory capacities and a unique sensory world. Reason and thinking, according to Bedil, represent the perfect higher stage of cognition.

In the philosophy of the 17th-18th centuries, the socio-philosophical views of Boborakhim Mashrab (1640-1711) are of particular significance. Mashrab was not only a passionate creator but also a courageous figure who could never reconcile with injustice and ignorance, earning great respect and recognition among the people. It is not known whether he ever compiled his works into a divan or collection. The social content and strong critical orientation in his works were shaped by his progressive worldview, folk-oriented philosophy, and his clear critical attitude toward negative events and phenomena of his time. His intellectual legacy also contains religious and Sufi ideas, as well as certain elements of Qalandariyya order, which was widespread in that era.

Thus, whereas previously a specialist's competence was understood mainly as the acquisition of certain knowledge and skills, today, based on emerging social needs, it is also necessary for individuals to possess forecasting skills aimed at the purposeful development of universal human abilities [5]. In the current stage of the development of education worldwide, the issue of philosophically and pedagogically substantiating the study and prediction of the social effectiveness of education is becoming increasingly relevant. Developing students' forecasting skills based on the teaching of philosophy is a specially organized process aimed at developing abilities that guide action, and is based on the probable tendencies in the scientific development of pedagogical reality objects or subjects. It is known that educational outcomes depend on the ratio of the two leading components of the learning process: the acquisition of knowledge (in our case learning the foundations of scientific forecasting) and the development of learners (developing thinking processes) [2]. The system of factors for developing students' forecasting skills based on teaching philosophy consists of three elements:

1. The knowledge component (a set of knowledge about forecasting as an integral part of an effective pedagogical process);
2. The activity component (a set of forecasting skills, professional and practical experience in forecasting);
3. The motivational component (a comprehensive view of the content of forecasting competence, understanding its significance, and readiness to develop this competence) [2].

The knowledge component is manifested as a set of knowledge in the field of forecasting that constitutes an integral part of effective pedagogical activity. As criteria for improving educational-cognitive competence, one should possess the following skills: setting goals and organizing their implementation, the ability to justify one's goals; forming cognitive tasks and making assumptions; analyzing one's learning activities; independently acquiring knowledge; applying reflection in one's educational-cognitive activity; self-assessment of one's cognitive work; presenting one's research results both orally and in writing.

The social-labor component includes planning professional activity based on scientifically grounded predictions; developing new forecasting experience during active educational and cognitive activity; and being aware of how to use forecasting in pedagogical activity [6]. The value-content and motivational component motivation, as an important factor regulating a person's activity, behavior, and actions, arouses interest in all individuals. In this sense, the psychology of motivation is of special importance for socio-economic professional groups in which a person is the main object of labor (such as doctors, teachers, managers, and administrators) [4]. The motivational component in forecasting appears as the necessity to learn and apply forecasting in everyday pedagogical practice.

The following factors play an important role in forecasting within effective education:

Adapting to new technologies: forecasting enables teachers to adapt to constantly changing technological requirements. Awareness of future trends helps integrate new educational technologies, which leads to more effective learning.

In the educational process, determining students' final knowledge and skills based on different criteria and approaches, as well as the use of information technologies, makes it possible to monitor how well they meet didactic requirements. In this process, pedagogical diagnostics includes identifying the level of formation of students' knowledge, skills, and competencies, monitoring and evaluating them, collecting and analyzing statistical data, and forecasting the development of this process in the future.

Considering individual needs: scientific forecasting involves analyzing the needs of each student, which makes it possible to create personalized educational programs. In turn, this ensures effective use of time and resources, and increases students' motivation and interest.

Foreseeing the educational requirements of the labor market. Forecasting in the field of education makes it possible to adapt curricula to the requirements of the labor market. This helps graduates acquire not only theoretical, but also practical skills, and contributes to the preparation of competitive specialists.

Optimizing the educational process. Knowing future changes makes it possible to optimize educational processes, prevent problems, and establish effective teaching methods.

Diagnostic assessments in the teaching process are considered important, because they help to some extent in choosing an effective methodology. In monitoring knowledge, its forecasting function serves to obtain information about the educational process, its future, that is, its state that can be foreseen in advance.

At each stage of the educational process, it provides an opportunity to check the prediction of whether the intended specific knowledge, skills, and competencies for a certain part of the educational material are sufficiently formed or not formed. The outcomes achieved based on scientific forecasting are used to create a model of the students' future activities. Such forecasting greatly helps in obtaining concrete conclusions for planning and implementing teaching in the future [1]. Mechanism parts that are interconnected and form a whole [7]. The mechanism of forming scientific forecasting should include two mutually complementary processes learning and development:

1. The informational block aimed at mastering knowledge that can serve as a basis for information-based forecasting (for example, knowledge about the development of students' personality), and is implemented through associative learning mechanisms;
2. The activity block technological activity aimed at mastering operational components, and is implemented based on algorithmic mechanisms;
3. The intellectual-creative block — aimed at the purposeful development of the qualities of thinking processes necessary for successfully carrying out activity, and is based on creative mechanisms.

The mechanisms of formation of the above-mentioned blocks are reflected in the methods of interaction between the future teacher and the student along with educational goals, content, and means [2]. For developing these directions of forecasting, a number of strategies can be integrated into the educational process. For example, in the method of designing and solving problematic tasks and situations related to the field of forecasting, each participant (teacher and student) is involved in the process, and the discussion is conducted bilaterally. In this case, the participants of the discussion work on and improve the ability to express their positions clearly

and fluently, oratory, finding solutions in a short period of time, viewing and analyzing the problem from various perspectives.

The factors of forming students' forecasting skills based on teaching philosophy are connected with many problems of pedagogical theory and practice. These include problems related to philosophical analysis, understanding pedagogical knowledge and pedagogical cognitive processes, methodological foundations of studying and forecasting the social effectiveness of education, the laws of forming and developing pedagogical forecasting, general conditions of constructing forecasting models, general scientific and specific principles of pedagogical forecasting, comparative historical-pedagogical analysis of main paradigms and strategies of pedagogy, developing the social efficiency of education in pedagogical theory and practice, studying and analyzing the experience of forecasting the social effectiveness of education, criticizing foreign and local models of educational social effectiveness built on various ideological, philosophical, and pedagogical foundations, and others.

Conclusion

Under the conditions of change of the current time, a dynamic approach aimed at describing the leading tendencies of social dynamics, a static approach providing the opportunity to understand the nature of social processes under relatively stable conditions, and the addition of problems revealing the situation, all foresee pedagogical forecasting within the system of interdisciplinary knowledge. In addition, the factors for forming students' forecasting skills based on teaching philosophy include solving problems of redefining the phenomenon of "knowledge" (such parts of knowledge are complex interdisciplinary, transdisciplinary, and interdisciplinary knowledge), issues of interdisciplinarity and multidimensionality that arise as a result of reinterpretation of knowledge, relativity issues, quality and effectiveness of modern educational systems, and participation in scientific research in the field of pedagogical prognostics.

REFERENCES

1. Djuraeva R.B. Formation of students' knowledge, skills, and abilities in teaching. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Innovations and Scientific Research in Uzbekistan*, 2022/13, Pp. 106-107.
2. Zakharov A.V. Mechanisms of forming prognostic abilities in future teachers. *Siberian Pedagogical Journal*, 2009, P. 270.
3. Mukhamadiev N.E., Mustafayev U.U. Radical reform of teaching philosophy in higher educational institutions a demand of the time. // Online scientific-practical conference at the ministerial level on "Philosophical issues of accelerating social development in the renewing Uzbekistan." Termez, 2020.
4. Nisanbaeva A., Chinalieva A. The importance of motivation in a person's activity. *Science and Innovation*, 2022, P. 781.
5. Stepanova L.N. *Pedagogical Education in Russia*, 2017/11, Pp. 109–110.
6. Saifullina N.A. Structural-content characteristics of prognostic competence of students in pedagogical magistracy, 2020/4, P. 74.
7. *Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language*. P. 584.